

Binary and Ternary Chelates of Scandium(III), Yttrium(III) and Lanthanum(III) with Ethyleneglycol-Bis (β -Aminoethylether)-Tetraacetic Acid as Primary and Substituted Salicylic Acids as Secondary Ligands

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Formation constants of binary and ternary complexes of the systems of the type : M-L and M-egta-L [M=scandium(III), yttrium(III) and lanthanum(III), egta=ethylene glycol-bis (β -aminoethylether)-tetra acetic acid, L=*o*-cresotic acid (*o*-ca), *m*-cresotic acid (*m*-ca), 5-chlorosalicylic acid (csa), and 3,5-dibromosalicylic acid (dbsa)] have been determined pH-metrically at 25° and $\mu=0.1M$ (KNO₃) in 50% (v/v) aqueous-ethanol medium. The order of stabilities of ternary complexes have compared with those of corresponding binary complexes, and results discussed on the basis of coulombic interactions.

DUE to the favourable geometry of its donor groups, ethyleneglycol-bis (β -aminoethylether) N,N,N,N'-tetraacetic acid (egta) forms stable complexes¹⁻³ with many metal ions at low pH values, but has not been used as a primary ligand in the study of ternary complex formation in solution. The work described here relates to an investigation of ternary complexes of several tripositive ions viz., Sc(III), Y(III) and La(III) with egta (as a primary ligand) and *o*-cresotic acid (*o*-ca), *m*-cresotic acid (*m*-ca), 5-chlorosalicylic acid (csa) or 3, 5-dibromosalicylic acid (dbsa) (as secondary ligand) adopting pH-metric titration techniques. Under identical conditions the binary complexes of the secondary ligands were also studied for comparison. All the experiments were carried out at 25° and at an ionic strength of 0.1 (KNO₃) in 50% (v/v) aqueous-ethanol medium.

It may mentioned here that the ternary complexes of these secondary ligands with 2, 2'-bipyridine (bipy)^{4, 5, 6}, 1,10-phenanthroline (phen)⁶ or nitrilotriacetic acid (nta)^{7, 8} as a primary ligand and several bipoisitive metal ions have been reported earlier from these laboratories.

Experimental

Solutions and related materials :

Reagents used were of analytical grade. Solutions of nitrates of Sc(III), Y(III) and La(III) were prepared and standardized, and suitable aliquots were diluted and nitric acid added (if necessary) to obtain 0.01 M metal(III) nitrate in 0.02 M nitric acid. Standard solutions of 0.1 M KOH, 0.02 M nitric acid and 1.0M KNO₃ were prepared as usual⁹. Stock

solutions of *o*-ca, *m*-ca, csa and dbsa (0.01 M each) in ethanol and an aqueous solution of egta (0.005 M) were prepared by direct weighing.

Instrument :

pH-measurements were made at 25° using expanded scale pH meter (Electronic Corp. of India) with glass-calomel electrode assembly supplied with the instrument.

Procedure :

(a) *M-L Systems* : Three titration mixtures (total volume 50.0 ml) viz., (a) acid, (b) ligand and (c) chelates were prepared. The concentrations were N°=0.1 M ; E°=.002 M ; TC_{L°}=0.001 M ; TC_{M°}=0.0002 M, symbols having usual meanings (4). Mixtures (a), (b) and (c) were individually titrated against standard alkali and thus three titration curves A, B and C were obtained for each system (figures omitted to economize space).

(b) *M-egta-L Systems* : The following mixtures (total volume 50.0 ml) were prepared (d) 5.0 ml nitric acid (0.02 M)+5.0 ml KNO₃ (1.0 M)+10.0 ml egta (0.005 M)+25.0 ml ethanol ; (e) 5.0 ml metal nitrate (0.01 M in 0.02 M HNO₃)+5.0 ml KNO₃ (1.0 M)+10.0 ml egta (0.005 M)+5.0 ml KNO₃ (1.0 M)+10.0 ml egta (0.005 M)+25.0 ml ethanol (f) 5.0 ml HNO₃ (0.02 M)+10.0 ml (0.02 M) nitric acid to account for the protons liberated as a result of complexation of egta with metal ion+5.0 ml KNO₃ (1.0 M)+5.0 ml of secondary ligand (*o*-ca,*m*-ca, csa or dbsa) (0.01 M)+20 ml of ethanol (g) 5.0 ml metal nitrate (0.01 M in 0.02 M nitric acid)+5.0 ml KNO₃ (1.0M)+10.0 ml egta (0.005 M)+5.0 ml secondary ligand (*o*-ca, *m*-ca, csa or dbsa) (0.01 M)+20 ml ethanol. The excess acidity in mixture (f) and (g) as compared to (a) was taken into account in the calcula-

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tions. The mixtures were separately titrated against standard alkali whereby four titrations curves viz., D, E, F and G in each case were obtained (figures omitted).

Calculations :

M-L Systems : The titration curves A, B and C were used to evaluate \bar{n}_A (average number of protons associated with the ligands) ; \bar{n} (average number of ligand molecules attached per metal ion) and pL (free ligand exponent). From these data the proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants were obtained (Table 1)^{5,6}.

\bar{n}_{mix} , average number of secondary ligand molecules attached per $(M-egta)^-$, as described earlier⁶. From the values of \bar{n}_{mix} so obtained, the values for free ligand exponent pL_{mix} were evaluated⁶.

The parameters \bar{n}_{mix} and pL_{mix} were treated similarly as in the binary systems to obtain formation constants corresponding to mixed ligand complexes formed (Table 1).

Results and Discussion

Binary complexing systems :

The values of proton-ligand stability constants obtained by average value method (Table 1) are in agreement with those reported earlier^{5,6}.

Only 1 : 1 binary chelates of Sc(III), Y(III) and La(III) could be studied with the ligands viz., *o-ca*, *m-ca*, *csa* and *dbsa*. Studies beyond 1 : 1 stage could not be carried out because of occurrence of opacity/turbidity/precipitation.

The stability order of metal chelates with respect to various ligands are : *m-ca* > *o-ca* > *dbsa* > *csa*. While those with respect to metal ions are Sc(III) > Y(III) > La(III).

Ternary complexing systems :

The values of $\log K_{M-egta-L}^{M-egta}$ [$K_{M-egta-L}^{M-egta}$ = mixed

ligand formation constant in M-egta-L systems] is less than $\log K_1$ [K_1 = first step formation constant of binary complexes of the secondary ligands]. This behaviour can be explained out the basis of coulombic interactions between various ligand anion species present. In the mixed ligand complex formation there is a repulsion between two negative charges from the secondary ligand anion and four negative charges from the *egta* anion. During the formation of ML species this type of repulsion is absent, which justifies $\log K_1 > \log K_{M-egta-L}^{M-egta}$. The stability order with respect to metal ions and the ligands follow the same pattern as those in binary complexing systems.

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TABLE 1—EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS IN BINARY AND TERNARY COMPLEXING SYSTEMS ; $\mu=0.1$ (KNO₃) ; 25° Equilibria log equilibrium constant

L (ligand) = <i>o-ca</i>	
$H^+ + L^2- \rightleftharpoons LH^-$	12.19 ± 0.09
$LH^- + H^+ \rightleftharpoons LH_2$	4.22 ± 0.08
$Sc^{3+} + L^2- \rightleftharpoons ScL^+$	10.11 ± 0.06
$Y^{3+} + L^2- \rightleftharpoons YL^+$	9.43 ± 0.02
$La^{3+} + L^2- \rightleftharpoons LaL^+$	8.26 ± 0.05
$[Sc(egta)]^- + L^2- \rightleftharpoons [Sc(egta)L]^2-$	5.72 ± 0.01
$[Y(egta)]^- + L^2- \rightleftharpoons [Y(egta)L]^2-$	5.59 ± 0.01
$[La(egta)]^- + L^2- \rightleftharpoons [La(egta)L]^2-$	5.42 ± 0.02
L = <i>m-ca</i>	
$H^+ + L^2- \rightleftharpoons LH^-$	12.29 ± 0.04
$LH^- + H^+ \rightleftharpoons LH_2$	4.10 ± 0.07
$Sc^{3+} + L^2- \rightleftharpoons ScL^+$	10.41 ± 0.04
$Y^{3+} + L^2- \rightleftharpoons YL^+$	9.65 ± 0.05
$La^{3+} + L^2- \rightleftharpoons LaL^+$	8.63 ± 0.03
$[Sc(egta)]^- + L^2- \rightleftharpoons [Sc(egta)L]^2-$	5.88 ± 0.01
$[Y(egta)]^- + L^2- \rightleftharpoons [Y(egta)L]^2-$	5.70 ± 0.01
$[La(egta)]^- + L^2- \rightleftharpoons [La(egta)L]^2-$	5.49 ± 0.02
L = <i>csa</i>	
$H^+ + L^2- \rightleftharpoons LH^-$	11.56 ± 0.09
$LH^- + H^+ \rightleftharpoons LH_2$	3.11 ± 0.05
$Sc^{3+} + L^2- \rightleftharpoons ScL^+$	9.07 ± 0.03
$Y^{3+} + L^2- \rightleftharpoons YL^+$	8.48 ± 0.03
$La^{3+} + L^2- \rightleftharpoons LaL^+$	7.75 ± 0.03
$[Sc(egta)]^- + L^2- \rightleftharpoons [Sc(egta)L]^2-$	5.21 ± 0.02
$[Y(egta)]^- + L^2- \rightleftharpoons [Y(egta)L]^2-$	5.06 ± 0.02
$[La(egta)]^- + L^2- \rightleftharpoons [La(egta)L]^2-$	4.86 ± 0.01
L = <i>dbsa</i>	
$H^+ + L^2- \rightleftharpoons LH^-$	12.05 ± 0.06
$LH^- + H^+ \rightleftharpoons LH_2$	2.86 ± 0.03
$Sc^{3+} + L^2- \rightleftharpoons ScL^+$	9.68 ± 0.01
$Y^{3+} + L^2- \rightleftharpoons YL^+$	8.84 ± 0.07
$La^{3+} + L^2- \rightleftharpoons LaL^+$	8.20 ± 0.07
$[Sc(egta)]^- + L^2- \rightleftharpoons [Sc(egta)L]^2-$	5.54 ± 0.02
$[Y(egta)]^- + L^2- \rightleftharpoons [Y(egta)L]^2-$	5.49 ± 0.01
$[La(egta)]^- + L^2- \rightleftharpoons [La(egta)L]^2-$	5.29 ± 0.01

The absence of polynuclear species etc was confirmed by repeating the experiments using several concentrations of the reactants, when the results obtained were identical.

M-egta-L Systems : It is observed that complete formation of $(M-egta)^-$ species occurs at a $pH \approx 4$, which remains stable even at higher pH values. Thus, the horizontal distance between curves (F) and (G) were measured and used for calculation of

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